

Thermal Behaviour of some Organotin(IV) Semicarbazone and Thiosemicarbazone Complexes

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Very little is known about the thermal behaviour of semi- and thiosemicarbazone complexes of transition and non-transition metals in spite of their diverse biological activities¹. In view of our interest in the study of the coordinating and thermal behaviour of these ligands towards transition elements² and organotin halides^{3,4}, we report herein the thermal studies of three new organotinsemicarbazone/thiosemicarbazone complexes, viz. $\text{Ph}_3\text{SnCl}(\text{FuFSCZ})$, $\text{Ph}_2\text{Sn}(\text{OHAcPhSCZ})$ and $\text{Ph}_3\text{Sn}(4\text{-MeBenzTSCZ})$.

Results and Discussion

The structures and stoichiometry of the complexes have been established by the various physicochemical and spectral studies as reported in our previous communications³. The complexes decompose in two steps in the temperature range 67–660° giving SnO_2 or $\text{SnO} + \text{S}$ as the end-product. Figs. 1–3 depict DTA, TG and DTG curves for $\text{Ph}_3\text{SnCl}(\text{FuFSCZ})$, $\text{Ph}_2\text{Sn}(\text{OHAcPhSCZ})$ and $\text{Ph}_3\text{Sn}(4\text{-MeBenzTSCZ})$, respectively.

As evident from TG curves, $\text{Ph}_3\text{SnCl}(\text{FuFSCZ})$, $\text{Ph}_2\text{Sn}(\text{OHAcPhSCZ})$ and $\text{Ph}_3\text{Sn}(4\text{-MeBenzTSCZ})$ are found to be stable upto 157, 87 and 94° respectively. The first step of decomposition of $\text{Ph}_3\text{SnCl}(\text{FuFSCZ})$ extends upto 315°, which corresponds to the loss of three phenyl groups, an half mole of chlorine and the organic skeleton of furan ring to give an intermediate (I), having the tentative composition $\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{N}_3\text{OSn}$ (Found : Sn, 56.48. Calcd. : Sn, 57.70%). It is accompanied by the weight-loss of 60.95% against the calculated

Fig. 1. DTA, TG and DTG curves of $\text{Ph}_3\text{SnCl}(\text{FuFSCZ})$.

value of 61.78%. This is observed in DTA and DTG as peaks at about 180 (endothermic) and 215, 250° respectively. A broad exothermic peak in DTA is also observed at 286° which may be due to the dominant effect of oxidation of organic skeleton to CO_2 . The second stage of the decomposition occurs between 320 and 560° and involves the loss of 3/2 mole of nitrogen and C_2H_5 group to give SnO_2 as an end-product. The corresponding observed weight loss is 10.59% compared to the calculated value of 10.21% along with an exothermic DTA peak at 495 and DTG peak at 517°.

The first stage of the decomposition of $\text{Ph}_2\text{Sn}(\text{OHAcPhSCZ})$ and $\text{Ph}_3\text{Sn}(4\text{-MeBenzTSCZ})$

Fig. 2. DTA, TG and DTG curves of $\text{Ph}_2\text{Sn}(\text{OHAcPhSCZ})$.

extends upto 370 and 345° to give the intermediate (I), having the tentative compositions $\text{C}_3\text{H}_5\text{N}_3\text{O}_2\text{Sn}$ (Found : Sn, 50.68; C, 14.85; H, 2.41; N, 18.00. Calcd. : Sn, 50.79; C, 15.40; H, 2.14; N, 17.97%) and $\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{N}_3\text{SSn}$ (Found : Sn, 51.90; C, 10.29; H, 1.71. Calcd. : Sn, 53.78; C, 10.87; N, 1.81%) respectively, which corresponds to the loss of phenyl groups in the molecule. The observed weight-losses were 49.51 and 58.18% compared

Fig. 3. DTA, TG and DTG curves of $\text{Ph}_3\text{Sn}(4\text{-MeBenzTSCZ})$.

to the calculated values of 49.63 and 60.43% for $\text{Ph}_2\text{Sn}(\text{OHAcPhSCZ})$ and $\text{Ph}_3\text{Sn}(4\text{-MeBenzTSCZ})$ respectively. The DTA and DTG curves of $\text{Ph}_2\text{Sn}(\text{OHAcPhSCZ})$ show peaks at 310 (exothermic) and 260° respectively, whereas a broad exothermic DTA peak maxima at 360° and a DTG peak at 299° are observed in case of $\text{Ph}_3\text{Sn}(4\text{-MeBenzTSCZ})$. An endothermic peak at 141° in the DTA curve of $\text{Ph}_2\text{Sn}(\text{OHAcPhSCZ})$ is also observed which may possible be due to the melting point of the complex.

The second and last stage of decomposition of $\text{Ph}_2\text{Sn}(\text{OHAcPhSCZ})$ and $\text{Ph}_3\text{Sn}(4\text{-MeBenzTSCZ})$ occurs between 375–660 and 360–550° respectively. The observed weight-loss was 17.48% as against the calculated value of 17.89%, which corresponds to loss of one mole of hydrogen and three moles of hydrogen cyanide to give SnO_2 as an end-product in case of $\text{Ph}_2\text{Sn}(\text{OHAcPhSCZ})$. The last stage of decomposition of $\text{Ph}_3\text{Sn}(4\text{-MeBenzTSCZ})$ corresponds to the observed weight-loss of 10.00% compared with the calculated value of 9.57% involving the loss of two moles of HCN, one mole of hydrogen and 1/2 mole of nitrogen to give a mixture of SnO and sulphur as an end-product. The DTA curves of $\text{Ph}_2\text{Sn}(\text{OHAcPhSCZ})$ and $\text{Ph}_3\text{Sn}(4\text{-MeBenzTSCZ})$ depict exothermic peaks at 440 and 530° respectively, whereas the corresponding DTG curves show peaks at 435 and 400, 450° respectively.

Intermediates have been characterised by ir spectral studies and the characteristic ir frequencies observed in their spectra correspond to their proposed structure. The end-product in each case also shows $\nu_{\text{Sn-O}}$ (540 cm^{-1}) and d values which are in close agreement with the reported values for either SnO_2 or SnO^5 .

On the basis of the above results, the following tentative schemes (Schemes 1–3) are proposed for the thermal decomposition of $\text{Ph}_3\text{SnCl}(\text{FuFSCZ})$, $\text{Ph}_2\text{Sn}(\text{OHAcPhSCZ})$ and $\text{Ph}_3\text{Sn}(4\text{-MeBenzTSCZ})$.

Scheme 1. Proposed scheme for decomposition of $\text{Ph}_3\text{SnCl(FuFSCZ)}$.

Scheme 2. Proposed scheme for decomposition of $\text{Ph}_2\text{Sn(OHAcPhSCZ)}$.

Scheme 3. Proposed scheme for decomposition of $\text{Ph}_3\text{Sn(4-McBenzTSCZ)}$.

Experimental

Details of analytical procedures and chemicals used are similar to those described earlier³. The complexes were prepared by the reported methods³. Thermal measurements were carried out using a Stanton Redcroft STA-780 thermal analyser, which simultaneously records DTA, DTG and TG curves. The sample (10–15 mg) was heated at a rate of 5° min^{-1} in a platinum crucible to a temperature of around 715° in static air. Alumina was used as a standard reference material, and the chart speed was maintained 20 cm h^{-1} . Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Beckman IR 20 spectrophotometer and X-ray diffraction patterns on a Philips diffractometer using $\text{CuK}\alpha$ radiation and a nickel filter at 35 kV.

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